

PROSPeCD

Pilot Research On a Scalable Population Health management Connected Dashboard

A Data 4PHM Project

Aim of this study

Effective data utilization is crucial for achieving **Population Health Management** (PHM). This proactive PHM addresses multidimensional population needs, utilizes a data-driven approach to identify care deviations, and prioritizes interventions.

Dashboards are essential to transform complex data into actionable insights through interactive visual interfaces. Despite existing disease-specific and multipurpose dashboards, Belgium lacks a comprehensive PHM dashboard that integrates diverse data types from different sources on multiple levels due to the limited, fragmented and non-interoperable data landscape.

Goals of this study

- Identification of content (e.g. data availability, analysis capabilities...), visual and access **requirements** for designing a PHM dashboard **tailored to the needs of potential users** (e.g. population health managers) and regional communities
- Identification of **implementation barriers and facilitators** of a PHM dashboard
- Development of a slide-based **mock-up dashboard**

Aim of this document

This document serves as a demo of the mock-up dashboard developed within the context of the PROSPeCD project. It is intended to provide a visual representation of the proposed functionalities and features. For a comprehensive understanding, these slides should ideally be reviewed alongside the detailed project report.

Last update 15/10/2024

Feedback

Your feedback on the PHM dashboard is highly valued as part of the **user-centered** and **iterative** development process.

Please share your feedback via: prospecd@kuleuven.be .

Feedback guidance

- Which visuals, content, accessibility, ... do you like in the dashboard?
- What do you find not/less desirable?
- Are there any features you consider complex?
- Which additional features are desirable?

Feedback categories

User need

- General exploration
 - Landing page, menu, metrics (e.g. data types and sources, description, ...), analysis options ...
- Risk stratification & intervention selection
 - PHM themes, selection of region, exploration of results (e.g. stratification, trends in time ...)
- Advanced data analysis
 - Database catalogue and dashboard, downloading and comparing metadata ...

User types

Visualization of analysis (e.g. color, pyramid, graphs ...)

Support (e.g. tips and cautions for using data, pop-ups to inform users about potential bias, identification of blind spots ...)

...

Population Health Management in Belgium

GET STARTED

URL should be discussed and agreed upon.

Colors, look & feel should be discussed and agreed upon.

Population Health Management in Belgium

GET STARTED

The footer of the landing page needs fine-tuning (e.g. funding statement, privacy notice). In addition, cookies should be defined and installed.

Focus on 3 main user needs

General exploration

Enabling users to conduct a broad exploration of population health management (PHM) within a specific region. It provides a comprehensive overview of various health outcomes, allowing users to identify risk factors without focusing on a single outcome. This exploratory approach is designed to uncover knowledge gaps, serving as a preliminary step before delving into specific health themes such as diabetes or high-risk pregnancies.

Risk stratification and selection of interventions

Supporting users who want to focus on a specific health theme. It allows them to identify at-risk sub-populations, compare regional data, and analyze trends in risk stratification over time. Additionally, it offers insights into recommended interventions aimed at shifting risk distributions (e.g., reducing pre-diabetes rates) and highlights which interventions are currently implemented or lacking in a particular region.

Research community

Targeted at expert users, this feature facilitates deep exploration of original data sources, including metadata cataloging. It is designed for those interested in initiating collaborative studies to investigate new research themes or pilot innovative approaches. This cluster supports advanced research activities within the community, fostering data-driven insights and innovation.

Focus on 2 types of users

Introducing user type 1: who they are, what they need and how we will support them

General
exploration

Risk stratification and
selection of
interventions

Research
community

Supported by a publicly accessible so-called '[PHM Dashboard](#)' - focusing on visualising validated PHM insights in a user-friendly way, requiring no log-in

'Population Health Manager'

This user is any individual who (aspires to) take(s) on the role of a 'Population Health Manager,' a role that can be fulfilled by people from various professional backgrounds, often without deep expertise in data science. Their primary focus is on 'general exploration' and 'risk stratification, as well as selecting interventions'. These users expect a user-friendly experience, enabling them to gain valuable insights quickly and intuitively without the need for extensive training. Additionally, they prefer to avoid administrative hurdles such as subscribing or logging in, allowing them to immediately start exploring the dashboard without any delays.

Focus on 2 types of users

Introducing user type 2: who they are, what they need and how we will support them

General
exploration

Risk stratification and
selection of
interventions

Research
community

Supported by the PHM Dashboard as well as the '[PHM Platform](#)', which requires a log-in and acceptance of terms and conditions. Data governance follows different legal frameworks based on usage. Users need a basic to advanced understanding of data science, depending on the chosen functionalities.

'Expert Population Health Management'

This user aspires to advance the field of population health management (PHM) in Belgium and takes on a pioneering role. While they might be a PHM researcher, this is not a requirement. They are deeply interested in exploring beyond the visualized data and are keen on understanding the data behind the graphs. This user is well-versed in population health management, capable of contextualizing preliminary insights, and motivated to uncover new findings. Moreover, this user is committed to collaborating with various stakeholders to enhance the dashboard's capabilities over time. They may also lead or participate in studies to generate new PHM insights. Willing to learn basic data science concepts (or already possessing advanced expertise), they are comfortable with minimal administrative steps, such as logging in, to access more advanced features.

Take me
to the PHM
dashboard

Log-in
to the PHM
platform

Alternative look & feel

- Cfr. suggestion to avoid visually splitting the website into two main sections (PHM dashboard versus PHM platform).
- Instead, a more seamless experience might be considered by focusing on the PHM dashboard in the user interface and placing a 'log-in' option on the top bar. Indeed, we assume that users of the PHM platform will be trained (and thus will find their way to the PHM platform), whereas users of the PHM dashboard may be less experienced.
- However, due to the significant differences in design and technical capabilities between the PHM dashboard and platform, the PHM dashboard versus platform are clearly separated for the purpose of this demo
- On the next slide a suggestion for a more nuanced integration is proposed

Population Health Management in Belgium

GET STARTED

Demo - User need 1

General
exploration

Risk stratification and
selection of
interventions

Research
community

Enabling users to conduct a broad exploration of population health management (PHM) within a specific region. It provides a comprehensive overview of various health outcomes, allowing users to identify risk factors without focusing on a single outcome. This exploratory approach is designed to uncover knowledge gaps, serving as a preliminary step before delving into specific health themes such as diabetes or high-risk pregnancies.

‘Population Health Manager’

Facilitated within the ‘PHM Dashboard’
Inspired by
www.cityhealthdashboard.com

'Landing page'

The footer of the landing page typically provides links to more background information on (data) governance (e.g. 'About the team', Privacy Policy, Terms of Use, ..), frequently asked questions, encourages feedback to ensure to stay user-focused, ...

'Landing page'

Features such as links to the latest research, reports, upcoming events, and impact stories can be included to provide users with relevant and updated content on population health management. This approach can help attract users to the dashboard even when they do not have a specific query, keeping them engaged through regular interaction. Additionally, offering a subscription to newsletters can further strengthen the connection with the user community by providing consistent updates and information directly to their inbox.

'Menu'

A user friendly 'menu' is a critical feature for the PHM Dashboard because it allows users to tailor their data exploration and analysis to specific needs and interest. The "Select a Metric" option allows users to immediately dive deep into a specific area of interest. In contrast, the "View Brookhaven, GA Overview" option provides a comprehensive summary of all available metrics for a given location.

Health Outcomes

- [Breast Cancer Deaths](#) UPDATED
- [Cardiovascular Disease Deaths](#) UPDATED
- [Colorectal Cancer Deaths](#) UPDATED
- [Diabetes](#)
- [Firearm Homicides](#) UPDATED
- [Firearm Suicides](#) UPDATED
- [Frequent Mental Distress](#)
- [Frequent Physical Distress](#)
- [High Blood Pressure](#)
- [Independent Living Difficulty](#) NEW
- [Life Expectancy](#)
- [Low Birthweight](#)
- [Obesity](#)
- [Opioid Overdose Deaths](#) UPDATED
- [Premature Deaths \(All Causes\)](#) UPDATED

Select a Metric

Social and Economic Factors

- [Broadband Connection](#) UPDATED
- [Children in Poverty](#) UPDATED
- [Chronic Absenteeism](#)
- [Credit Insecurity Index](#)
- [High School Completion](#)
- [Income Inequality](#) UPDATED
- [Neighborhood Racial/Ethnic Segregation](#) UPDATED
- [Racial/Ethnic Diversity](#) UPDATED
- [Rent Burden](#) UPDATED
- [Third-Grade Reading Scores](#) UPDATED
- [Unemployment](#)
 - [Current, City-Level](#) UPDATED
 - [Annual, Neighborhood-Level](#) UPDATED
- [Voter Turnout](#) NEW

Health Behavior

- [Binge Drinking](#)
- [Physical Inactivity](#)
- [Smoking](#)
- [Teen Births](#)

Physical Environment

- [Air Pollution - Ozone](#) UPDATED
- [Air Pollution - Particulate Matter](#) UPDATED
- [Housing with Potential Lead Risk](#) UPDATED
- [Lead Exposure Risk Index](#) UPDATED
- [Park Access](#)
- [Walkability](#)

Clinical Care

- [Dental Care](#)
- [Prenatal Care](#)
- [Preventive Services, 65+](#)
- [Routine Checkup, 18+](#)
- [Uninsured](#) UPDATED

OR

[View Brookhaven, GA Overview](#)

Metrics Overview for Brookhaven, GA

Scale bar min/max values: Brookhaven, GA Census Tracts

Lighter colors indicate better outcomes

Legend for metrics: City or census tract value, Dashboard-City Average, Present when value is better than Dashboard-City Average, Better Outcomes Average.

CLICK ON A METRIC FOR MORE DETAIL. INFORMATION ON THIS PAGE REFLECTS THE MOST CURRENT YEAR OR MONTH AVAILABLE. HIDE ALL

Health Outcomes

Grid of health outcome metrics: Breast Cancer Deaths, Cardiovascular Disease Deaths, Colorectal Cancer Deaths, Diabetes, Firearm Homicides, Firearm Suicides, Frequent Mental Distress, Frequent Physical Distress, High Blood Pressure.

Expanded view of Frequent Mental Distress: 14.3% vs 16.2% average. Includes description, source (PLACES Project), and a map of Brookhaven area.

See Metric Detail

Grid of health outcome metrics: Independent Living Difficulty, Life Expectancy, Low Birthweight, Obesity, Opioid Overdose Deaths, Premature Deaths (All Causes).

Grid of social and economic factors: Neighborhood Racial/Ethnic Segregation, Racial/Ethnic Diversity, Rent Burden, Third-Grade Reading Scores, Unemployment - Annual, Neighborhood-Level, Unemployment - Current, City-Level, Voter Turnout.

Health Behavior

Grid of health behavior metrics: Binge Drinking, Physical Inactivity, Smoking, Teen Births.

Physical Environment

Grid of physical environment metrics: Air Pollution - Particulate Matter, Housing with Potential Lead Risk, Park Access, Walkability, Prenatal Care, Preventive Services, 65+, Uninsured.

Learn more about these metrics

This overview presents a broad snapshot of various health outcomes, social and economic factors, health behaviors, and environmental and clinical care indicators for the chosen area. This approach is useful for users who want a holistic view of the region's overall health profile or who may be exploring the data without a specific metric in mind. The overview helps users understand the general health landscape of the area before deciding which specific metrics warrant a deeper dive.

Metrics Overview for Brookhaven, GA

Scale bar min/max values: Brookhaven, GA Census Tracts

Lighter colors indicate better outcomes

- City or census tract value
- Dashboard-City Average
- Present when value is better than Dashboard-City Average
- Better Outcomes Average

CLICK ON A METRIC FOR MORE DETAIL. INFORMATION ON THIS PAGE REFLECTS THE MOST CURRENT YEAR OR MONTH AVAILABLE. HIDE ALL

Health Outcomes

Breast Cancer Deaths <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>	Cardiovascular Disease Deaths <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>	Colorectal Cancer Deaths <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>
Diabetes	Firearm Homicides <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>	Firearm Suicides <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>
Frequent Mental Distress	Frequent Physical Distress	High Blood Pressure

Frequent Mental Distress

Brookhaven had an estimated 14.3% of adults report frequent mental distress in 2021, compared to an average of 16.2% across the Dashboard's cities.

Description: Percentage of adults who report ≥14 days of poor mental health in the past 30 days

Source: PLACES Project, Centers for Disease Control. Data from 2021, 1 year modeled estimate.

See Metric Detail

Independent Living Difficulty	Life Expectancy	Low Birthweight <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>
Obesity	Opioid Overdose Deaths <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>	Premature Deaths (All Causes) <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>

Specific metrics can be explore in more detail very simply by clicking on a 'dropdown sign'. Another interesting features presented here is visualization of the region of interest in comparison with the surrounding regions, using intuitive color schemes

Neighborhood Racial/Ethnic Segregation	Racial/Ethnic Diversity	Rent Burden
Third-Grade Reading Scores	Unemployment - Annual, Neighborhood-Level	Unemployment - Current, City-Level
Voter Turnout		

Health Behavior

Binge Drinking	Physical Inactivity	Smoking
Teen Births <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>		

Physical Environment

Air Pollution - Particulate Matter	Housing with Potential Lead Risk
Park Access	Walkability

Dental Care	Prenatal Care <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>	Preventive Services, 65+ <i>Data not available. Click for more.</i>
Routine Checkup, 18+	Uninsured	

Learn more about these metrics

'Demographics Overview'

'Demographics overview' provides high-level descriptive information about the region of interest. In Belgium, interesting similar resources are e.g. 'Provincies in Cijfers'

More about Brookhaven, GA

Brookhaven is located in DeKalb County, Georgia, northeast of Atlanta. It officially became a city in 2012.

Explore county data for [DeKalb County](#) and [Fulton County](#) on the [County Health Rankings & Roadmaps](#) site.

These data tables describe the age and race/ethnicity demographic distribution of the city's population. Policymakers, community-based organizations, city residents, and others working in these communities can use these data to target outreach and resources intended to promote and advocate for health among these groups. These data are not linked to the other metrics on the Dashboard.

About the Data

Data displayed here are from 2022 American Community Survey (ACS) 5-year estimates provided by the U.S. Census Bureau. Racial/ethnic subgroups are included based on both ACS data availability and expert consultation.

Displaying these data required numerous decisions, including how to categorize racial/ethnic groups and when to include foreign-born data. For a full explanation of these decisions, click [here](#).

Race/Ethnicity and % Foreign-born <small>Categories are not mutually exclusive, so population percentages may not sum to 100.</small>	POP %
Any race/ethnicity, foreign-born	19%
Asian Alone, foreign-born	4.5%
Black or African American Alone, foreign-born	1.4%
Hispanic or Latino, foreign-born	8.8%
White Alone, not Hispanic or Latino, foreign-born	4%
American Indian and Alaska Native	6%
+ Asian	9.4%
Black or African American	12.2%
+ Hispanic or Latino	17.6%
+ Native Hawaiian or Other Pacific Islander	0.2% ¹
White, not Hispanic or Latino	59.1%

Age	POP %
Age 0-17	22.2%
Age 18-64	67.6%
Age 65+	10.2%

'Compare regions'

Allowing comparisons of regions to be made easily is crucial since it provides insights into relative outcomes

‘Compare metrics’ Map

By allowing the display of multiple metrics —such as e.g. ‘Frequent Mental Distress’ and ‘Life Expectancy’—on a map, users can assess how these metrics align or diverge across various regions, providing a visual tool to explore the correlation between complex health relationships. This feature helps to highlight geographic patterns and encourage deeper investigation into the potential connections between different health outcomes and determinants.

Metric Comparison Map

This map shows the census tract values of Frequent Mental Distress and the census tract values of Life Expectancy in Brookhaven, GA. This map can help you understand general geographic patterns for both metrics at the same time and how they might relate to each other.

Caution is important when examining metric comparison maps; just because two metrics are lower or higher in the same neighborhood does not mean that one causes the other.

Frequent Mental Distress

Life Expectancy

'Compare metrics'

Scatterplot view

The "Scatterplot View" presents an alternative way to visualize potential correlations between metrics by plotting data points on a graph instead of using a map. This plot shows the relationship between two variables: Frequent Mental Distress and Life Expectancy. Unlike the map view, which offers a geographic perspective, the scatterplot focuses on the statistical relationship between the metrics, allowing users to quickly identify trends, clusters, or outliers in the data. This approach provides a clearer picture of how two variables may be related across different locations without the geographic context that a map provides.

Scatterplot View

This plot shows the census tract values of Frequent Mental Distress plotted against census tract values of Life Expectancy in Brookhaven, GA. Each point represents a census tract within Brookhaven.

Caution is important when examining scatterplots: just because two items are correlated does not mean that one causes the other.

You can click on a point to see the values for a specific census tract.

Tips and caution: introduction

- Pop-ups will be installed to intuitively inform users about potential biases that may occur when interpreting the dashboard.
- Initial examples of how these pop-ups can be operationalized are provided in the next slide
- Important Note: The risk of misinterpretation can occur and is most likely to happen. This underscores the need for a help desk to facilitate and support broader use, ensuring users can get the necessary assistance to interpret the data and insights from the dashboard correctly.

Tips and caution: examples

EXAMPLE

Broadband Connection

Brookhaven had an estimated **80,1%** of households with high speed broadband internet in **2021**, compared to an average of **75,8%** across the Dashboard's cities.

Description:

Percentage of households with high speed broadband internet connection (cable, fiber optic, DSL)

Source:

American Community Survey, U.S. Census Bureau. Data from 2021, 5 year estimate.

Tips and caution: examples

EXAMPLE

! Tips and Cautions for Using the Data

SHOW

! Tips and Cautions for Using the Data

HIDE

- Users may notice city or census tract boundary changes when moving between years of data, especially for 2020. This is due to updated boundaries from the US Census and the Decennial Census. [Learn about changing Census boundaries.](#)
- We do not recommend using these Broadband Connection data to assess exact year-to-year differences because each estimate reflects a pooled estimate across multiple years of data, resulting in overlapping years across estimate. [Click here](#) for more.
- Multi-year data should not be used to evaluate the impact of local public health programs or policies. Please see "MORE ABOUT METRIC" section above for details on data years.
- Census tract boundaries may not perfectly align with city boundaries. Use caution when interpreting estimates for census tracts on the edges of the city because values may include data from populations that live outside the city. [Click here](#) for more.

EXAMPLE

Scale bar min/max values: ?

‘Download data’: introduction

- A desire to export the underlying data from the dashboard for further analysis and exploration has been expressed. The needs of data scientists will be primarily addressed through the "PHM platform" (more details in the following slides) which is designed to cater to users with advanced data analysis skills, unlike the PHM dashboard that focuses on individuals with limited data science background.
- In the ‘PHM dashboard’ we could allow the option to ‘download data’, after providing more details and accepting high-level terms of use. An example of how this could go is provided in the next slide

‘Download data’: example

 DOWNLOAD Data for More Analysis

The PROSPeCD Dashboard Data Use Agreement

Please complete this short survey in order to access the PROSPeCD Dashboard’s data available for download

Email address

First name

Last name

Institution

I am a... (dropdown-list): e.g. researcher, student, population health manager, ...

I am downloading these data.. (dropdown list): e.g. for a project at school, at work, to understand more about my region, ...

By clicking on Proceed below, I have read and agree to abide by the PROSPeCD Dashboard’s Terms of Use

Demo - User need 2

General
exploration

Risk stratification and
selection of
interventions

Research
community

‘Population Health Manager’

It is supporting users who want to focus on a specific health theme. It allows them to identify at-risk sub-populations, compare regional data, and analyze trends in risk stratification over time. Additionally, it offers insights into recommended interventions aimed at shifting risk distributions (e.g., reducing pre-diabetes rates) and highlights which interventions are currently implemented or lacking in a particular region.

Facilitated within the ‘PHM Dashboard’
Inspired by
PHM blueprint van Nottingham

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

Prevention
Diabetes
Type II

Prevention
Cardio-
vascular
disorders

Well-
Being of
Health
Care
professionals

Care for
psychological
suffering

Multi-
morbidity

Chronic
obstructive
pulmonary
disease

**COMING
SOON**

**COMING
SOON**

**COMING
SOON**

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know.

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

Prevention
Diabetes
Type II

Prevention
Cardio-
vascular
disorders

Well-
Being of
Health
Care
professionals

- *The definition of these themes requires further refinement with input from experts to ensure accuracy and relevance.*
- *The number of available themes will expand over time (Link with the 'PHM Platform' - More information will be provided in the upcoming slides.*
- *Prioritization of themes will be determined through discussions with stakeholders. This prioritization will consider both the needs of the stakeholders and the feasibility of creating reliable dashboards for each theme. Feasibility factors include, among others, the complexity of the theme and the availability and quality of relevant data.*

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know.

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

Average prevalence of diabetes II

- 0-5%
- 5.1-10%
- 11-15%
- 16-20%
- >20%

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

Other statistics can be visualized here if desired (e.g. costs related to diabetes care). If needed, even multiple options could be facilitated

Average prevalence of diabetes II

Definitions of categories should be done in consultation with experts to make sure it is useful

In this stage, we are demonstrating the principle of the 'Select Your Region of Interest' feature using a map of Belgium. Population health managers can choose specific regions for analysis and intervention planning. The current prototype showcases the basic functionality of region selection.

Future discussions with technical partners will explore and finalize the interaction methods, which may include:

- Tick-boxes for selecting and deselecting regions.
- Click and unclick functionality directly on the map.
- Mouse scanning to highlight and select regions.
- Other innovative selection techniques as deemed feasible by our technical team.

These options will be evaluated in a later stage to ensure the most user-friendly and efficient experience for our population health managers.

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Did not find what you are looking for? Check-out the PHM platform or let us know

High need

Diabetes

Pre diabetes

Healthy

Compare results with another region

See trends in time

Identify intervention

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know

Compare results with another region

See trends in time

Identify intervention

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

High need

Diabetes

Pre diabetes

Healthy

- Diagnoses with T2 Diabetes
- BMI >30
- No energy/strength to perform activities: shopping, cleaning, driving, walking
- Not achieving optimal glucose control/remission
- Undertakes fasting for cultural or religious believes
- One or more health or care conditions
- Mental health, Renal disease, CKD, frail, etc.
- Not achieving two or more optimal Blood pressure > Cholesterol, HbA1c
- Smoker/social substance misuse
- Drinks >14 units of alcohol in a week daily
- Pregnant/history of gestational diabetes
- Not up to date/partially up to date with imms and vacs/screening

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

521

5%

High need

This is just an example. The definitions of the indicators used to segment the populations require further refinement with input from experts (Link with the 'PHM Platform' - More information on this will be provided in the upcoming slides.)

2

3.5

5.214

45%

Healthy

- Diagnoses with T2 Diabetes
- BMI >30
- No energy/strength to perform activities: shopping, cleaning, driving, walking
- Not achieving optimal glucose control/remission
- Undertakes fasting for cultural or religious believes
- One or more health or care conditions
- Mental health, Renal disease, CKD, frail, etc.
- Not achieving two or more optimal Blood pressure > Cholesterol, HbA1c
- Smoker/social substance misuse
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- Pregnant/history of gestational diabetes
- Not up to date/partially up to date with imms and vacs/screening

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Select a comparator region.

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “Leuven” as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Select a comparator region

Similar to the comment raised earlier, we are demonstrating the principle of the 'Select Your Region of Interest' feature using a map of Belgium. Population health managers can choose specific regions for analysis and intervention planning. The current prototype showcases the basic functionality of region selection.

Future discussions with technical partners will explore and finalize the interaction methods, which may include:

- Tick-boxes for selecting and deselecting regions.
- Click and unclick functionality directly on the map.
- Mouse scanning to highlight and select regions.
- Other innovative selection techniques as deemed feasible by our technical team.

These options will be evaluated in a later stage to ensure the most user-friendly and efficient experience for our population health managers.

5.2

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “Leuven” as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

8.413

Total number of individuals in Noord-Limburg

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

Did not find what you are looking for? Check out the PHM platform or let us know

Step 1:
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Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected "diabetes" as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected "Leuven" as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

11.423

Total number of individuals in Leuven

High need

Diabetes

Pre diabetes

Healthy

Choose the sub-population you are interested.

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “Leuven” as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “diabetes” as your sub-population of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

Nice guidelines recommend that all people with diabetes should receive the following health care check at least once a year

- HbA1c
- Blood pressure measurement
- Cholesterol test
- Eye screening
- Foot Examination
- Kidney function
- Urinary albumin
- BMI measurement
- Smoking review

Percentage of individuals with diabetes in Leuven receiving repetitive health care check

Step 1:
Select your PHM theme of interest

Step 2:
Select your region of interest

Step 3:
Explore the results

You have selected “diabetes” as the theme of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “Leuven” as region of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

You have selected “diabetes” as your sub-population of interest. Go back and adjust this when needed.

Nice guidelines recommend that all people with diabetes should receive the following health care

This is just an example. The definitions of the indicators that are used to segment the populations requires further refinement with input from experts (Link with the 'PHM Platform' - More information on this will be provided in the upcoming slides.)

- Kidney function
- Urinary albumin
- BMI measurement
- Smoking review

Current situation for Leuven

Average across Belgium

Percentage of individuals with diabetes in Leuven receiving repetitive health care check

The possibility to compare with other regions as well as to consults the results in time can be facilitated (in line with the previous slides)

Demo - User need 3

General
exploration

Risk stratification and
selection of
interventions

Research
community

‘Expert Population Health Management’

Facilitated within the ‘PHM Platform’
Inspired by
[EHDEN portal](#)*

Targeted at expert users, this feature facilitates deep exploration of original data sources, including metadata cataloging. It is designed for those interested in initiating collaborative studies to investigate new research themes or pilot innovative approaches. This cluster supports advanced research activities within the community, fostering data-driven insights and innovation.

Take me
to the PHM
dashboard

Log-in
to the PHM
platform

PHM Platform

You can use (or [create](#)) a local account

The image shows a login form with two input fields. The first field contains the email address 'liesbet.peeters@uhasselt.be' and is preceded by a person icon. The second field contains a masked password represented by seven dots and is preceded by a key icon. Below the password field is a link that says 'Forgot your password?'. A blue 'Sign in' button is positioned below the link. At the bottom of the form, there are two links: 'Feedback' and 'About'.

liesbet.peeters@uhasselt.be

.....

[Forgot your password?](#)

Sign in

[Feedback](#) · [About](#)

EXAMPLE

Study idea: Detecting cases of delayed pregnancy follow-up from the field.

Welcome to the EHDEN Portal

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The EHDEN Portal provides an entry point to the growing list of tools in our ecosystem. **Of these tools, Database Catalogue (including Dashboards) and EHDEN Academy are available for general use, while Arachne, Atlas and the Service Desk are still in development and only available to EHDEN Consortium members.** Click on the icons below for more information. Your [feedback](#) is highly appreciated.

Database Catalogue

Provides metadata on the databases in the EHDEN data network.

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Enables the comparison of OMOP CDM databases.

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Our free, online and publicly available learning platform.

Publications

An overview of all deliverables and publications of EHDEN.

ARACHNE

Orchestration tool for research studies (available soon).

ATLAS

Scientific analyses on the OMOP CDM (available soon).

Service Desk

Management/tracking of service requests (available soon).

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PORTAL

>>

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PORTAL

Welcome to the EHDEN Portal

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The EHDEN portal utilizes open-source software, allowing for extensive customization to meet the specific needs of the Population Health Management (PHM) platform.

This flexibility includes, but is not limited to:

- Modifying text content to better suit the requirements and context of the PHM portal.
- Defining own terms and conditions for user log-in processes.
- Specifying the questions and parameters to be included in the meta-data catalogue.

Specifically, for this page, it means that we can adjust the text as we see fit to align with our strategic objectives and user needs.

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An overview of all deliverables and publications of EHDEN.

ARACHNE

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Scientific analyses on the OMOP CDM (available soon).

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Management/tracking of service requests (available soon).

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Home icon

Database icon

Dashboard icon

Academy icon

Search icon

PORTAL

Notifications icon

Calendar icon

Phone icon

Profile icon

Share icon

Welcome to the EHDEN Portal

The **European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN)** project aspires to be the trusted observational research ecosystem to enable better health decisions, outcomes and care. Its mission is to provide a new paradigm for the discovery and analysis of health data in Europe, by building a large-scale, federated network of data sources.

The EHDEN Portal provides an entry point to various tools (EHDEN Dashboards) and EHDEN Academy are available to EHDEN Consortium members.

Database Catalogue
Provides metadata on the databases in the EHDEN data network.

Publications
An overview of all deliverables and publications of EHDEN.

The Database Catalogue is designed to assist end-users with specific study requirements or research questions by enabling them to browse metadata profiles of various databases. This detailed cataloguing is crucial in reducing the time required to discover relevant data sources, facilitating collaborative research efforts.

The Catalogue collects descriptive information on various aspects of each database, including governance, purpose, inclusion criteria, procedures for data quality control, and details on how and which data is collected. Since it consists solely of metadata or descriptive data, it poses very limited to no privacy concerns.

Additionally, when data sources have mapped their data to the OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) using open-source tools from the OHDSI community, the descriptive data and quality assessment can be updated automatically.

The Catalogue meets several user needs, such as:

- Viewing available databases
- Filtering and ordering databases based on specific criteria
- Comparing different databases
- Exporting metadata from databases

This tool is a valuable resource for researchers, making it easier to identify and utilize appropriate data sources for their studies.

>>

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PORTAL

205 Results

Sorted by: Database Acronym

Select all

	2CA-Braga	2CA-Braga Academic Clinical Center - Braga	1M Portugal	<input type="checkbox"/>
	ABUCASIS	ABUCASIS Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA	3.88M Spain	<input type="checkbox"/>
	ACI	Auria Clinical Informatics at Turku University Hospital Hospital District of Southwest Finland (HDSF)	765K Finland	<input type="checkbox"/>
	ADWH IMR			

Here, all data sources that are contributing meta-data are listed for instance, the EHDEN portal Image this to be leveraged to the PHM portal; examples of data sources that would be listed here include Intego, IMA-AIM, FarmaFlux, among others.

For more detailed information about which data sources could, should, or would be included in the PHM platform, please refer to the 'Frequently Asked Questions (and Answers)' section.

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Home icon

Menu icon

Dashboard icon

Calendar icon

Search icon

Settings icon

PORTAL

Bookmarks icon

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Profile icon

Logout icon

Databases / ABUCASIS

- Fingerprint
- Database Dashboard

Hits: 579 Unique Views: 343 Filled: 91.7 %

Summary Collapse

DATABASE DESCRIPTION

For enquiries about this database, please contact enquiries@ehden.eu.

Database Acronym: ABUCASIS

Database Name: ABUCASIS

Institution name: Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA

Department name: Proyectos en Bigdata

Street Address: Avenida Menendez y Pelayo 4 acc

City: Valencia

1. Database Description (20/20)	100%
2. Contact Details (10/10)	100%
3. Technical Details CDM (5/5)	100%
4. Data Governance and Ethics (9/9)	100%
5. Publications (1/2)	50%

When you click on a specific data source, such as 'ABUCASIS,' you will have two options: 'The Fingerprint' (this slide) and 'The Database Dashboard' (see next slide).

The Fingerprint allows you to consult the metadata, offering a comprehensive overview. The questions and details in this section can be adjusted to meet our needs. This flexibility ensures that the metadata presented is relevant and useful for end-users, facilitating a deeper understanding of the data source.

Navigation sidebar with icons for home, search, and other functions. User profile: Liesbet Peeters.

The Database Dashboard provides an overview of summary statistics for a specific data source. This dashboard will give you a snapshot of key metrics and statistical information. This includes data volume, patient demographics, and other relevant statistics that offer a quick understanding of the database's scope and content. This feature is designed to help users quickly assess the value and relevance of a data source for their research or study needs.

Databases / ABUCASIS

Fingerprint Database Dashboard

Database-Level Dashboard

Number of Patients

4.01M

Gender

gender	number of records
FEMALE	2.06M
MALE	1.95M

Gender

Age at first observation

Distribution of age at first observation period

Another valuable feature available in the Catalogue is the ability to compare metadata for up to four different data sources. This functionality allows end-users to evaluate and contrast various databases, helping them identify which ones best meet their specific requirements. For instance, users can compare data sources based on their indicators, such as the volume of patient records or specific demographic details. This comparative analysis helps users make informed decisions about which data sources are most suitable for their research or study needs, ensuring they select the most relevant and valuable databases for their objectives.

+ Expand all 🔑 Show/Hide ▾

To filter questions, type your keywords here Comparing 3 databases

	ADWH IMR Reference ▾	ABUCASIS Compared ▾	aGMS Compared ▾
Database Description	Database Description	Database Description	Database Description
Database Acronym	ADWH IMR	ABUCASIS	aGMS
Database Name	Anonymized Data Warehouse- IMR	ABUCASIS	aggregate Gargano Mortality Study
Institution name	Innovative Medical Research S.A.	Instituto de Investigación Sanitaria INCLIVA	Fondazione I.R.C.C.S Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza
Department name	Innovative Medical Research S.A.	Proyectos en Bigdata	Research Unit of Diabetes and Endocrine Disease
Street Address		Avenida Menendez y Pelayo 4 acc	Viale Padre Pio
City	Athens	Valencia	San Giovanni Rotondo
Postal code		46010	71013
Country	Greece	Spain	Italy
Website	https://www.imrdiagnostics.gr/	https://www.incliva.es	https://www.operapadrepio.it/it/ricerca-scientifica/gruppi-di-ricerca/endocrinologia
Database description	The anonymized database of the Innovative Medical Research S.A., one of the highest quality and most competitive providers of medical- diagnostic services in Greece serving more than 300,000 people annually in the region of Attica- Greece and offering a wide range of medical and diagnostic ISO-certified services, is a real-world database which has been developed by integrating data from one of the largest networks of primary healthcare units in Greece and	INCLIVA/ABUCASIS database contains information about 3,800,000 persons from the Valencia Region (Spain). Every included person is above 18 years old. Source database contains a single record for each person. This record contains both inpatient and outpatient information, including diagnosis, medical and surgical procedures, imaging and laboratory tests, and drug prescriptions among others. Source database is anonymized following	The data source gathers information about people affected by Type 2 Diabetes collected by Fondazione IRCCS Casa Sollievo della Sofferenza in San Giovanni Rotondo (Foggia) starting from 2000 and followed until now for all-cause mortality and renal function decline. The data, captured from inpatient electronic health record, concern demographic and anthropometric features (e.g. age, sex, BMI), lifestyle habits (e.g. smoking habits and physical exercise),

Job Queue

Task	Start Date	End Date	Progress	Status	Output
Export of selected database answers in EHDEN - July 04, 2024, 01:33 PM	July 4, 2024, 2:33 p.m.	July 4, 2024, 2:33 p.m.	100.00 %	✓	Download

Another feature of interest in the Catalogue is the ability to download the metadata of different data sources. This metadata is summarized in a CSV or Excel file, allowing end-users to perform additional statistics and/or create custom visualizations independently. Please note that this download feature is limited to metadata only, and users are bound by the terms and conditions of the PHM platform when using these files. This capability provides users with the flexibility to further analyze and utilize the metadata according to their specific needs.

[Close](#)

Order By

Database Acronym ▼

Ascending Descending

Filter By

Database Acronym

Database Name

Total number of patients

 to

Institution name

Country

Last Update

The Catalogue also offers advanced functionalities to 'order' or 'filter' the databases based on specific metadata features. This enables users to tailor the database listings to meet their needs, enhancing their search and selection process.

Users can apply filters such as country, date of the last update, or the total number of patient records. These filtering options allow users to quickly navigate through the extensive data source listings and focus on those that are most relevant to their research criteria. This feature is especially useful for efficiently identifying the most suitable databases for specific studies or analyses.

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Enables the comparison of OMOP CDM databases.

EHDEN Academy

Our free, online and publicly available learning platform.

The Network Dashboard is a powerful tool developed by the European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN) to enable comparison of OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) databases across the network. This web application aggregates information from distributed OMOP CDM databases, providing users with a graphical overview of the data.

The Network dashboard presents detailed graphical representations of database characteristics. This lets users gain insights into population demographics, data domains, and other important metrics.

Key Differences between the Catalogue and the Network Dashboard

- **Functionality Focus:** The Catalogue is primarily a tool for discovering and browsing metadata of databases, making it easier to find relevant data sources. The Network Dashboard, on the other hand, is focused on detailed graphical analysis and comparison of the data within these databases.
- **User Interaction:** The Catalogue allows users to view, compare, and download metadata, whereas the Network Dashboard provides interactive graphical dashboards for in-depth analysis and comparison.
- **Data Presentation:** The Catalogue deals with metadata in a more textual and tabular form. At the same time the Network Dashboard presents data visually, using charts and graphs to highlight key metrics and comparisons.

Feedback

Your feedback on the PHM dashboard is highly valued as part of the **user-centered** and **iterative** development process.

Please share your feedback via: prospecd@kuleuven.be .

Feedback guidance

- Which visuals, content, accessibility, ... do you like in the dashboard?
- What do you find not/less desirable?
- Are there any features you consider complex?
- Which additional features are desirable?

Feedback categories

User need

- General exploration
 - Landing page, menu, metrics (e.g. data types and sources, description, ...), analysis options ...
- Risk stratification & intervention selection
 - PHM themes, selection of region, exploration of results (e.g. stratification, trends in time ...)
- Advanced data analysis
 - Database catalogue and dashboard, downloading and comparing metadata ...

User types

Visualization of analysis (e.g. color, pyramid, graphs ...)

Support (e.g. tips and cautions for using data, pop-ups to inform users about potential bias, identification of blind spots ...)

...